

PRIMARY CHARACTERISTICS OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AT THE SOCIAL SERVICE OF BANTEN PROVINCE

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Abstract

Along with the times, advanced organizations are required to be able to adapt and continue to make changes. The development of an organization is largely determined by the individual performance of each member of the organization in carrying out each task and workload. Every organization always demands its employees to be able to work productively and professionally. Employee performance problems are certainly influenced by several factors, or in other words the level of performance of an employee depends on the factors that influence it. In addition, the current challenges of globalization have implications for changes in organizational structure, both government organizations and corporate organizations. Changes that occur in the external and internal environment related to the development and improvement of organizational capabilities, cannot be separated from the importance of human resources. This study uses a qualitative method with a grounded theory approach, while the purpose of this study is to determine the primary characteristics of organizational culture in the social service of Banten Province, and the results of this study explain that the characteristics of organizational culture in the implementation of the Banten Province Social Service are determined by innovation and courage. risk taking, Attention to detail, Result oriented, Human oriented, Team oriented, Aggressive and Stability. All of these seven characteristics cannot be separated, they influence each other, are interrelated and there are dimensions that participate in strengthening the characteristics of organizational culture in the Banten Province Social Service organization, namely the Commitment and Competency Dimensions. However, the organizational characteristics of the Banten Province Social Service are not only determined by the seven primary characteristics of organizational culture but are also determined by the dimensions of commitment and competence with the aim of realizing an independent and competitive Social Service, thus strengthening the theory and modifying the theory of organizational culture characteristics. foundation and must exist and be integrated in the Banten Province Social Service organization.

Keywords: Characteristics, Organizational Culture, Social Service

A. INTRODUCTION

Primary characteristics Organizational culture is an organizational personality or organizational characteristics which is a manifestation of the organization that reflects its uniqueness, especially reflected in the attitudes, behavior and orientations or perspectives of each member of the organization that is integrated in the organization's resources. human resources as a State Civil Apparatus, norms, employee behavior, skills, integrity, attitudes, actions, competencies and commitments to the organization (Akpa et al., 2021; Sidiq et al., 2021).

The primary characteristics of organizational culture at the Banten Provincial Social Service are seen as still weak and do not reflect a strong culture as a public organization oriented to public services. Various phenomena of problems, the complexity of service organization activities starting from human resources and organizational resources and related to the

knowledge framework or cognitively contained in Human Resources as employees, employees or in the State Civil Apparatus. Thus, organizational culture is an important variable and must be strong, especially in realizing work planning, work processes (government management), work results to work evaluations or evaluations in organizations, especially at the Banten Province Social Service.

Organizational culture helps shape and strengthens organizational activities in an effort to realize the achievement of the Governor and Deputy Governor's vision and mission as well as the organizational goals of the Social Service. Achieve organizational success. In terms of realizing a strong organization, internal strength of the organization is needed as a form of organizational capability, especially in attitudes, behaviour and actions as well as the direction of the goals set which are reflected in the characteristics of the organization that can be used as strength for the organization, especially in the Banten Province Social Service organization. The Banten Provincial Social Service has the main task, namely providing services to the public, formulating organizational policies, including public services that are attached to the roles and organizational functions of the Banten Provincial Social Service, especially in improving social welfare services for the Banten people (Ariani & Gayatri, 2021; Prawira et al., 2021).

Banten Province Social Service in general has not shown significant success, especially in the field of Social welfare in Banten Province due to weak organizational characteristics which are reflected in organizational management which includes planning, processes and work results through collaboration, coordination, which is manifested in organizational work activities and makes an organizational characteristic that is even integrated with the values of belief (bealief) held by members of the organization, from the leadership to members of the organization, from the bureaucracy to the components of the service organization as well as the activities of organizational units in the public service process, including in the policy achievement process. as well as programs at the Banten Province Social Service which so far have not shown significant success.

The importance of organizational culture has implied that organizations are human tools. So, when someone establishes an organization, the ultimate goal is not the organization itself but so that he/the people and all those involved in it (the organization) can achieve the goals more easily and more effectively. The achievement of organizational goals is stated in the 2017-2022 Strategic Plans (Renstra) for the Banten Provincial Social Service. What has been done in social service governance has only reached 35%, this is a problem that needs to be solved by the Banten Province Social Service. There are several programs that are quite effective in overcoming social welfare in Banten Province, including the Social Assistance Program in order to increase the effectiveness and accuracy of targeting social assistance distribution and to encourage financial inclusion (Wiludjeng et al., 2019; Sidiq et al., 2021).

In connection with the foregoing, the role of the Banten Province Social Service organization is very strategic in realizing social welfare for the realization of a more prosperous and just standard of living for the people of Banten. Thus, it is necessary to optimize the role of the Banten Province Social Service organization so that the Social Service organization is

stronger and more effective in carrying out all its duties and responsibilities as public servants. In accordance with development priorities and agendas, the social welfare development program is a very strategic program.

The Banten Provincial Government continues to strive to alleviate social welfare problems by providing grants and social assistance such as the Jamsosratu program which has been recognized by the central government as successful in reducing poverty in Banten. However, it needs to be acknowledged, on the other hand, that the government's social institutions owned by Banten Province are still limited in handling social rehabilitation for Persons with Social Welfare Problems (PMKS), meaning that the Banten Provincial Government has not been maximal in handling social problems in detail (Attention to Social Welfare). detail), this is contrary to the Regulation of the Minister of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia no. 9 of 2018 concerning Basic Service Technical Standards on Minimum Service Standards in the Social Sector in Provincial Regions and in Regency/City Areas where in handling the Provincial Government provides Minimum Service Standards (SPM) services for (1) basic Social Rehabilitation of Abandoned Persons with Disabilities in Social Institutions (2) Basic Social Rehabilitation of Abandoned Children in Social Institutions (3) Basic Social Rehabilitation of Abandoned Elderly Persons in Social Institutions (4) Basic Social Rehabilitation of Socially Impaired Children, especially Homeless and Beggars in Social Institutions and (5) Protection and Social Security at during and after Disaster Emergency Response for Provincial Disaster Victims (Nashori & Ma'rifatullah. 2019).

Based on the 2015 integrated database (PBDT) update, data on poor households (RTM) in Banten Province amounted to approximately 645 thousand RTM. While those covered by the Family Hope Program (PKH) are 310 thousand KPM, and those covered by Jamsosratu are only 50 thousand KPM. Based on this context, the Office of Social Affairs as an organization has not obtained optimal results, namely not outcome orientation, the extent to which management focuses attention on results rather than on the techniques and processes used to achieve those results, which results in results not being achieved. Weak aggressiveness (aggressiveness) of people or apparatus who tend to be relaxed in carrying out work programs, especially in carrying out their main tasks and functions. Based on this context, the community's enthusiasm and concern for various social problems in Banten need to be improved so that social problems can be handled gradually.

Efforts to solve social problems are not an easy thing, but with the enthusiasm and concern of all of us, including the Social Welfare Coordinating Institute (LKKS), these problems can be resolved more quickly. LKKS as social welfare institutions in cities and districts has an important and strategic role in dealing with poverty problems, as well as strengthening family functions, including in fostering various social institutions in the regions that still need to be optimized (Geert, 2003).

The primary characteristics of organizational culture will be strong and able to make a positive contribution in building the effectiveness of the organization in achieving its goals, strengthening policy capabilities and precisely policy objectives related to solving organizational problems as a whole and this depends on the strength of the characteristics of

the organizational culture. That is, the stronger the organizational culture will encourage the organization's capability to achieve goals. On the other hand, if the organizational culture is weak, the policies and performance of the organization will also be weak, so it does not encourage the capability of organizational policies (Farhan et al., 2021).

The phenomena, facts and data described above show evidence of weak primary characteristics of organizational culture at the Social Service of Banten Province, it can be seen from various organizational dynamics at the service, the behavior of organizational members at the service has not shown an attitude that is integrated with the organization, even some of the employees do not reflect an attitude of integrity caused by not understanding the meaning of organizational culture consistently, firmly and deeply. In fact, culture in an organization helps members of the organization provide responses or responses to ambiguity and difficulties in completing work, problems and efforts to build organizational policy capabilities, so it is reasonable to say that the primary characteristics of organizational culture at the Banten Provincial Social Service are weak, so they have not been able to achieve organizational goals. Organizational management, good and clean governance and does not yet guarantee fair, transparent, professional and accountable interactions between the parties concerned.

B. METHOD

The method used in this research is a qualitative research method. Qualitative methods begin with various phenomena in real-life conditions in accordance with the conditions on the object of research. In. The approach used in this study, namely the grounded theory approach, is research that uses inductive techniques and emphasizes participatory observation efforts between the variables studied, so that the research carried out prioritizes in-depth analysis and usually contains several stages in the implementation of a research. Sources of data in this study in the form of primary and secondary data that became the basis of the analysis. Primary data sources in the form of empirical situations and conditions of the Service carried out in the field obtained from informants in the form of information and data from interviews with parties based on their social status related to the existence of employees and leaders. While secondary data comes from documents and photos, archives, journals, scientific works and statistical data from the government, the public and mass media publications. Furthermore, the data collection and recording technique in this study was carried out by field observations by looking at the work process by conducting interviews with related parties, including, observation, in-depth interviews (Jufrizen & Rahmadhani, 2020).

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Building Characteristics of Effective Organizational Culture at the Banten Province Social Service

The results of research on the primary characteristics of organizational culture at the Social Service of Banten Province provide a general description, namely that there are strong cultural characteristics and weak cultural characteristics, both of which greatly affect organizational behavior. Every organization has its own culture that is specific due to the fact

that every organization has a unique (unique) personality which is influenced by various things, including; the characteristics of the organization as well as the values and norms held by its members, beliefs, habits prevailing in the organization, and the organizational philosophy adopted. This encourages organizational members to behave in certain ways within the organization that can affect all employee activities in the organization, whether working, how to view work, working with colleagues, or looking to their future and being a differentiator from one organization to another. Organization is a social unit or social entity established by humans for a relatively long period of time, consisting of a group of at least two human beings, having coordinated, organized and structured activities, established to achieve certain goals and having a self-identity that distinguishes one entity from other entities. (Juliana, 2019).

The description of the organization at the Banten Province Social Service shows that there are several main characteristics that reflect the existence of an organization in behavior and which differentiates it from other organizations that distinguish one organization from another, namely; social unit/entity, consisting of at least two people, structured work pattern, has goals to be achieved and has a self-identity. These characters can be understood through the dimensions of organizational characteristics originating from the internal organization and overall organizational characteristics which are determined by the size (big/small) of the organization, the technology used the organizational environment, its goals and culture. Organizational culture shows certain characteristics, traits, or characteristics that show similarities. The roots of organizational culture are a set of core characteristics that are collectively valued by all members of the organization. Organizational culture characteristics show the characteristics, traits, elements, or elements contained in an organizational culture. Each organization will show its characteristics and characteristics based on the characteristics of its organizational culture.

The Banten Province Social Service, which is a public organization, has realized that it is believed that the existing organizational culture greatly influences the optimization of employee performance and organizational performance which is also correlated with efforts to realize the vision and mission it carries, namely realizing an advanced and competitive social service organization. On the other hand, employees have been encouraged to be motivated by the leadership to be innovative, work in detail, but so far there have been no significant changes so that there have been no new breakthroughs in organizational management to make the Banten Provincial Social Service more advanced and strong in line with the vision and mission. (Irmayanthi & Surya, 2020).

The situation is quite prominent, especially in technical activities in the field because it involves services to the community to overcome poverty, immorality, people with mental disorders, disabilities, natural disasters which are quite challenging and are faced with sick people, poor people, and disaster situations by having to travel through the area. And terrain that is far away and has high risk and threatens the safety of life with various program activities and support from a fairly large budget. This reality is faced by the social service even though it is not sufficiently supported by qualified, competent, and skilled human

resources. General description and work patterns that exist between employees who prioritize feelings, morals, and heart compared to professionalism and competence.

This fact can be a peculiarity in work interactions between employees in the social service and this is a characteristic of employee performance that may be a characteristic that distinguishes it from other employees outside the social service so that they accept what is in their work, under the pretext of dedication and very show attitude. which is not dynamic, not aggressive so that they (employees) feel safe and comfortable and this can be understood because government organizations tend to be colour by power, are seen as lasting without threats, are very static, rigid and inflexible in responding to the environment so that they tend to behave "client patrons" wait for orders and are very far from being dynamic, aggressive and innovative because they consider government organizations with identities as Civil Servants/ ASN to be guaranteed safe, and can retire. So it is very natural that they work as they are and this is very in line with their understanding of the vision and mission of the Banten Province Social Service organization (Ruskawan, 2017).

Organizational culture is an important component of an organization that has the power to determine and define its relationship with organizational performance and sustainability. It has always been considered to have a profound and important impact on various organizational processes, employees and performance and an important element for unifying various organizational cultures/companies within groups/teams within the organization/company structure". This can be interpreted that the importance of organizational culture becomes a new source of strength in improving organizational performance to achieve the organization's vision and mission and has even become the foundation, so that organizational development can no longer rely solely on organizational hardware. On the other hand, organizational culture is a major component of daily organizational functions because performance has been considered to depend on efforts to achieve the vision and mission as a characteristic of organizational culture.

The primary characteristics of organizational culture at the Banten Provincial Social Service are closely related to its vision and mission, even the organizational performance and employee performance must be in the same direction and able to achieve and make it happen. However, so far the organization and even organizational resources, especially employees in general, do not know and do not understand it. In part, the opinion of employees is that the existing vision and mission is the provincial vision and mission not the service or who states that the vision and mission of the Regional Head is not the vision and mission of the social service. That is, this occurs due to a lack of socialization to provide an understanding of employees. A vision is a goal, a future, a goal, a thing to do. Mission is a step, form or method and how to make it happen. Vision is the big picture or overall picture of what you want. Mission is the description of what will be done to achieve or realize the vision. This meaning is not understood by most employees in social services and employees only have thoughts and understanding, "what is important is that we work and can produce and complete it, regardless of process and analysis, which is important to finish oriented to work results" (Sinclair, 2014).

Internally the organization at the Banten Province Social Service is illustrated in the form of organizational capabilities, especially in attitudes, behavior and actions in work as well as the direction of the goals set which are reflected in organizational characteristics that can be used as strengths for the organization, especially in the Banten Province Social Service organization that is very dependent on the leadership (Head of Service and Secretary of Service). The Banten Province Social Service has shown a caring attitude in line with its main task, namely providing services to the public, formulating organizational policies, including public services that are attached to the organizational roles and functions of the Banten Province Social Service, especially in improving social welfare services for the Banten people. The Banten Provincial Social Service as one of the Banten Province Regional apparatuses. It is clear that through the Head of Service and the Secretary of the Service, they are always trying to realize the vision of Banten development 2017–2022, namely, Banten which is advanced, independent, competitive, and prosperous and has good character.

In the Banten Province Social Service organization, it is known that the role of organizational culture has a real impact on the behavior of organizational members as individuals, groups or as a whole organization. Basically, organizational culture will foster identity in each of its members and their attachment to the organization, because the similarity of embedded values will make it easier for each member of the organization to understand and live every event and activity carried out by the organization. An understanding of organizational culture at the Banten Provincial Social Service, in addition to facilitating the resolution of internal problems at the service, such as those relating to rewards, work ethic and career development, also helps the organization in dealing with problems related to adjustment to its external environment, so that the organization can continue to survive in all conditions. . The acceleration of environmental change at the Banten Province Social Service resulted in a change in organizational culture. For example, that the Banten Provincial Social Service's vision and mission are based on the Regional Head's vision and mission so that it has an impact on employees thinking that the vision and mission is not the Social Service's vision and mission but the Regional Head's vision and mission. This factually occurs in the field, so it is natural that most of the Social Service employees do not understand the Office's own vision and mission because in general, individuals are motivated by a culture that influences their behavior.

Factors Causing Weak Primary Characteristics of Organizational Culture at the Social Service of Banten Province

There are factors that cause the weakness of the primary characteristics of organizational culture at the Banten Provincial Social Service so that this can hinder the achievement of the goals, vision, mission of the realization of an advanced and competitive organization. Commitment factor is not optimal, because basically organizational commitment can grow because individuals have emotional ties to the company which include moral support and accept the values that exist within the company and determination from within to serve the company. In a company, it is very necessary to have a clear and directed commitment in achieving company success. Organizational commitment is a condition in which an employee

sided with a particular organization and the goals and desires to maintain membership in the organization (Suhermanudin, 2016).

In addition, organizational commitment is also an attitude that reflects employee loyalty to the organization and the ongoing process in which members of the organization express their concern for the organization. Organizational commitment can grow from an emotional bond with the company which includes moral support, values in the company and the inner willingness to serve the company. It can be interpreted that organizational commitment is the identification of a person's involvement in the organization to maintain membership in the organization and is willing to strive for the achievement of organizational goals. Indeed, employees have a high organizational commitment if they have trust and accept the goals and values of the organization, are willing to strive towards achieving organizational goals, and have a strong desire to survive as members of the organization. In addition, organizational commitment as employee trust accepts organizational goals and chooses to stay and not leave the organization.

There are also other factors that encourage the emergence of weaknesses in the Social Service organization, including the competence factor of employees. In fact there are seventy employees who are not in accordance with the educational background and only ten employees who are in accordance with the educational competence background of the employees and they also tend to be passive and not aggressive. From this definition, it can be interpreted that competence is a characteristic that underlies a person related to the effectiveness of individual performance in his work or basic characteristics of individuals that have a causal relationship with criteria that are used as references, effective or excellent or superior performance at work or in certain situations. In accordance with the Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform of the Republic of Indonesia Number 38 of 2017 concerning Competency Standards for State Civil Apparatus Positions, the position competencies that must be possessed by every State Civil Apparatus (ASN) are technical competence, managerial competence, and socio-cultural (cultural) competence. (Maggara & Frinaldi, 2021).

Culture requires individuals to behave and instruct them on what to follow and learn. However, this condition has not been developed effectively in the Banten Provincial Social Service so that the decline in organizational performance is mostly due to changes in the characteristics of its organizational culture, because organizational culture is one type of intangible asset belonging to the organization. Therefore, based on the results of research to realize the characteristics of an effective organizational culture at the Social Service of Banten Province, it is necessary to link the seven characteristics of organizational culture expressed by Robbins (2013: 212-213) which includes the integration of innovation and the courage to take risks, attention to detail, orientation to results, people oriented and team oriented. Modifying the seven characteristics of organizational culture with the dimensions found by researchers who participated in strengthening the characteristics of organizational culture in the Banten Province Social Service organization, namely dimensions, commitment and competence.

Efforts are needed to build the characteristics of organizational culture at the Banten Provincial Social Service because organizational culture greatly influences individual

behavior and overall organizational behavior. Organizational culture is essentially a system of shared meaning that is embraced by its members as employees and becomes a characteristic and differentiator from other organizations. Therefore, the characteristics of organizational culture as a key to success need to be built and strengthened because in the Banten Province Social Service organization there are values that shape the behavior and work standards that are determined, these conditions can make the achievement of the overall goals of the organization's vision and mission effective.

Leaders in this regard have a very large role in building the characteristics of an effective organizational culture at the Banten Provincial Social Service. Leaders have a contribution as a creator and shape the characteristics of the Social Service organizational culture, because they have the ability and power to influence. In addition, that the Social Service must have a vision and mission that is in line with the Regional Head and not have the exact same parent as the current one, but that the service has derived from the vision and mission of the regional head with the same meaning and essence (Aziza, 2015).

Commitment from all parties must be strong and consistent in line with the achievement of the vision and mission of the service besides being urgently needed to create competent employees (having Competence), then the leadership provides an example and spreads it which is then followed by his subordinates. The growth of traits and styles in leadership character is triggered by the important role of organizational culture, so the higher the quality of leadership, the stronger the perception of each member (employees/subordinates) regarding the characteristics of organizational culture.

Building organizational culture in the Banten Social Service organization is largely determined by the effective implementation of the 7 (seven) characteristics of organizational culture expressed by Robbins (2013:212-213) which include the integration of innovation and the courage to take risks; Attention to detail; Results oriented; Human oriented; Team oriented; Aggressiveness ; Stability. However, based on the findings of researchers in the field, there are dimensions found by researchers who participate in strengthening the characteristics of organizational culture in the Banten Province Social Service organization, namely the dimensions of Commitment, and Competence. In addition, there has been a vision and mission of the service organization that has been determined, even though it is seen that the vision and mission is politically influenced by the Regional Head (Governor & Deputy Governor) which should be specifically determined together within the scope of the Provincial Social Service while remaining linear with the vision the contents of the Regional Head (Nia et al., 2017).

Building an effective organizational culture in the Banten Social Service organization is an effort to instill organizational cultural values in public management or public administration, this can be done by streamlining and strengthening the 7 (seven) characteristics of organizational culture and adding 2 (characteristics) , namely strengthening the Commitment and Competence to achieve the organizational vision and mission of the Social Service and continuously making improvements in management/administration with continuous improvements. Affective commitment or emotional self-involvement in the organization, namely the willingness of employees to try their best for the benefit of the organization. To be able to create employees who have customer-oriented abilities, employees who love their

work are needed so that they will do their work wholeheartedly, this may arise when employees have an attachment to their organization. Organizational expectations of employees can identify the company's vision and mission and are committed to being actively involved in activities, this is a manifestation of a strong organizational culture characterized by commitment because employees who have emotional attachment to the organization are said to have affective commitment. Affective commitment is a condition when individuals consider the extent to which their values and goals are in accordance with the values and goals of the organization.

Affective commitment is part of organizational commitment which refers to the emotional side attached to an employee related to his involvement in a characteristic of a strong organizational culture. Employees who have a strong affective commitment will always be loyal to the organization they work for because the desire to survive comes from their heart. Affective commitment can arise because of a need, and also a dependence on activities that have been carried out by the organization in the past that cannot be abandoned because it will be detrimental. This affective commitment is formed as a result of an organization that can make employees have strong beliefs to follow all organizational values, and strive to realize organizational goals as the first priority, and employees will also maintain their membership (Munandar et al., 2020).

There is a strong correlation between employee commitment and competence because it is related to the level of organizational performance. Affective commitment is the most desired form of commitment by the company as a manifestation of the consequences and responsibility of employees to the organization, while optimizing the performance of each employee is largely determined by their competence so that what employees do is in accordance with their educational background, abilities, and expertise. where as a manifestation of the characteristics of a person or individual related to the effectiveness of performance in the organization and or optimal performance in a job and certain circumstances by having the ability to adapt to the work environment. Competence as a basic characteristic is part of an individual's personality which is relatively deep and stable, it can be seen and measured from the behavior of the individual concerned at work or in various situations. So that it can be interpreted that a person's competence is an indication of a person's ability to behave in a variety of situations that is quite consistent for a fairly long period of time and is not a mere coincidence.

Competence is closely related to the quality of services provided to the external community, often determined by the quality or quality of services provided by employees. Organizations at the Banten Province Social Service are expected to be able to encourage the participation of their employees in making service improvements so that the quality of service to customers/community can be maintained and of good quality. Customer/community satisfaction is built on several principles used by organizations by having a strong culture in providing tangible, reliable, test-resistant, responsive, empathetic, and accountable or accountable services (Sartika & Pragiwani, 2020, 2020).

The results of the observations and interviews above can be interpreted that there are still many problems faced by employee orientation, so the motivational factor from the leadership is a very important key to improve employee performance and on the other hand there is no

solution to overcome this and not all existing employees do not. have specific skills so that competence becomes an important factor that employees need to have with the appropriate skills needed. The results in the field also explain that employee orientation, there are no functional staff who are expert and professional. Team Orientation. Social workers only exist as social workers with a chemical education background and continue until now, even though the formation is needed by the Banten provincial government.

Human Factors viewed from the management's point of view is the main resource and also sees human resources as an asset that functions as a supporter to achieve the goals or targets of achieving the organization's vision and mission. But when we talk about human capital, this concept sees people as the key in the organization, not just a supporter to achieve goals. In it, he will focus on maximizing the ability of employees or human resources so that the organization's strategy can run effectively as it should. Thus, employees as one of the organizational assets cannot be easily replaced by others (Mochamad, 2015).

The statement from the Head of the UPT for Social Protection above was strengthened by the Secretary of the Social Service and also from the staff of the staff at the Banten Province Social Service stating that the orientation to Humans is not yet fully in accordance with the specifications of expertise. The absence of competent experts is because social people tend to behave in ways that can work, can help and can provide meaning. The work climate of employees at the Banten Provincial Social Service is stuck in the soul as an employee at the service, namely that work is dedication. This is a very good organizational culture to be embedded in all employees. However, unfortunately, most employees are not based on a professional spirit and most employees are not in accordance with their competencies so that it has a bad impact on work results because the "skills" they have are not in accordance with their field of work (Nahrul, 2020).

Humans in organizational culture have a very important and strategic role so that they can be viewed as investments or as "human capital". Literally, the notion of human capital can be interpreted as human capital. It can be further described, that human capital is a collection of aspects of knowledge, skills, abilities, and skills which make a human being an asset in an organization that will strengthen the organizational culture. This is an added value for the organization in carrying out its daily operations through motivation, competence, skills, and teamwork. Contributions given by employees can be in the form of developing employee skills to increase organizational productivity, transforming knowledge possessed by leaders, employees to the organization, and will be adaptive to changes and will even strengthen the existing culture within the organization.

D. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this research is that the characteristics of organizational culture in the implementation of the Banten Provincial Social Service are determined by innovation and the courage to take risks, attention to detail, results orientation, human orientation, team orientation, aggressiveness and stability. All of these seven characteristics cannot be separated, they influence each other, are interrelated and there are dimensions that participate in strengthening the characteristics of organizational culture in the Banten Province Social

Service organization, namely the Commitment and Competency Dimensions. The conclusion of this study basically strengthens the theory and modifies the theory of Robbins about the primary characteristics of organizational culture to be implemented in the Banten Province Social Service organization in order to have strong organizational culture characteristics that can achieve and realize the vision and mission of the organization. Thus, the results of the modification of the theory that the researcher put forward were nine dimensions or characteristics of organizational culture. Factually, the characteristics of organizational culture at the Banten Provincial Social Service are divided into two categories, namely strong culture and weak culture. However, the organizational characteristics of the Banten Province Social Service are not only determined by the seven primary characteristics of organizational culture but are also determined by the dimensions of commitment and competence with the aim of realizing an independent and competitive Social Service, thus strengthening the theory and modifying the theory of organizational culture characteristics. foundation and must exist and be integrated in the Banten Province Social Service organization.

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